

THE SUPPORT OF A GENERALIZED FUNCTION

Koshmuratova Gulnaza Muxtarovna

2nd grade student, Kaakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19594275>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 09th April 2026

Accepted: 11th April 2026

Online: 13th April 2026

KEYWORDS

In particular, if for every φ , then the generalized functions f and g are said to be equal in the domain G , and this is written as $f = g$ in the domain G .

ABSTRACT

It should be emphasized that a generalized function does not have a value at a specific point. Nevertheless, it is possible to speak of a generalized function vanishing (being equal to zero) in a domain.

It should be emphasized that a generalized function does not have a value at a specific point. Nevertheless, it is possible to speak of a generalized function vanishing (being equal to zero) in a domain.

Definition 1. If $(f, \varphi) = 0$ for every $\varphi \in D(G)$, then the generalized function f is said to vanish (be equal to zero) in the domain G , and this is written as $f = 0$ for $x \in G$ or $f(x) = 0$ for $x \in G$.

Definition 2. If $(f - g, \varphi) = 0$ for every $\varphi \in D(G)$, then the generalized functions f and g are said to be equal in the domain G . This is written as $f(x) = g(x)$ for $x \in G$.

In particular, if $(f, \varphi) = (g, \varphi)$ for every $\varphi \in D$, then the generalized functions f and g are said to be equal in the domain G , and this is written as $f = g$ in the domain G .

Let the generalized function f vanish in the domain G . In that case, this generalized function vanishes in the neighborhood of every point within that domain G . The converse statement is also true.

Lemma 1. If a generalized function f is equal to zero in a neighborhood of every point of the domain G , then this generalized function f is also equal to zero in the domain G .

Let $f \in D'$ be a generalized function. The set O_f , which is the union of all neighborhoods where $f = 0$, is an open set, and this set is called the zero set of the generalized function f . According to the proven lemma, $f = 0$ in any domain located within the set O_f ; furthermore, the set O_f is the largest open set that satisfies the condition $f = 0$.

Definition 3. The complement of the set O_f with respect to the space R^n is called the support of the generalized function f and is denoted as $\text{supp } f$.

According to this definition, $\text{supp } f = R^n \setminus O_f$, and it is a closed set.

Definition 4. If the support $\text{supp } f$ is a bounded set, then the generalized function f is called a finitary function (or a distribution with compact support)

From these definitions, we draw the following conclusions:

a) The generalized function f vanishes in any domain lying outside of its support $\text{supp } f$; that is, for any $\varphi \in D$ such that $\text{supp } f \cap \text{supp } \varphi = \emptyset$, we have

$$(f, \varphi) = 0. \quad (1)$$

b) The support of a generalized function f is the set of points, and only those points, such that in any neighborhood of each point, the generalized function f does not vanish

Lemma 1 can be generalized as follows. If $f \in D'(G)$ and $G' \subset G$ is a domain such that $G' \subset G$, then for any $\varphi \in D(G')$, a linear functional $f_{G'}$ is defined by the equality

$$(f_{G'}, \varphi) = (f, \varphi).$$

This functional $f_{G'}$ is continuous in the space $D(G')$ in the following sense: if the sequence $\varphi_k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ in the space $D(G)$ and $\text{supp } \varphi_k \subset G' \subset G$, then $(f_{G'}, \varphi_k) \rightarrow 0$ at $k \rightarrow \infty$. Usually, the functional $f_{G'}$ is called the local element of the generalized function f in the domain G' (also referred to as the restriction of the generalized function f to the domain G').

Thus, every generalized function creates its own local element in every domain. The converse statement is also true: for any set of consistent local elements, a unique generalized function can be constructed by means of "gluing" (or "patching"). More precisely, the following theorem holds true.

Theorem 1 (The Gluing Theorem / Patching Lemma). Suppose that for every point $y \in G$, there exists a neighborhood $U(y) \subset G$ in which a generalized function f_y is given; furthermore, if $x \in U(y_1) \cap U(y_2)$, let $f_{y_1}(x) = f_{y_2}(x)$ on the intersection $U(y_1) \cap U(y_2)$. In that case, there exists a unique generalized function $f \in D'(G)$ such that for every point $y \in G$, the generalized function f coincides with f_y in the neighborhood.

References:

1. Михайлов В.П. Дифференциальные уравнения в частных производных. М. Наука, 1983 год.
2. Тихонов А.Н., Самарский А.А., Уравнения математической физики, М-Л., изд. 2-е, Гостехиздат, 1953.
3. Ладженская О.А. Краевые задачи математической физики. Наука, 1973 год.
4. Владимиров В.С. Уравнения математической физики. Наука, 1971.

Б.Ш.Г.Касимов, Т.Н.Аликулов, Ш.К.Отаев, Ғ.С.Хаитбоев, М.М.Бабаев “Математик физиканинг замонавий усуллари” 1-2 том.

